

Quality Analysis via Computer Vision Using PyTorch and IoT Connectivity for Data Visualization

Arthur Alves Meister

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1939-1641>

Ellen Cardoso Silva Nascimento

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0980-522X>

Ingrid Mangia Barros

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1858-7391>

Matheus de Almeida Silva

<https://orcid.org/0009-0003-1614-6760>

Nicolas Silva de Paula

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6832-8358>

Vitor Amadeu Souza

<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-1857-6799>

Abstract—This paper presents the development of a quality inspection system based on Computer Vision, Machine Learning, and the Internet of Things (IoT) for classifying cut-resistant gloves as defective or non-defective. Transfer Learning was applied using the ResNet-18 architecture in Python (PyTorch), encompassing data collection and pre-processing, model training and validation. The solution integrates real-time video capture, automatic decision-making, communication with the Thinger.io platform, LED actuation via Arduino, and speech synthesis. Results indicate high classification performance and demonstrate the viability of the proposal as a support tool for industrial quality control, aligned with Industry 4.0. One hundred tests were conducted, with an average inference time of 43.23 ms and an accuracy of 89%.

Index Terms—Computer vision; Machine learning; IoT; Defect classification; Industrial automation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Industry has undergone technological transformation throughout history, from the first stone tools to modern production systems. These changes were marked by four industrial revolutions:

- 1) **First Industrial Revolution:** characterized by the use of steam engines, mechanization, and the emergence of factories.
- 2) **Second Industrial Revolution:** expansion of electricity, steel, assembly lines, and new mass-production methods.
- 3) **Third Industrial Revolution:** automation, electronics, information technology (IT), and robotics for controlling industrial processes.

We are currently living through the **Fourth Industrial Revolution**, also known as Industry 4.0, characterized by real-time connectivity, intensive use of data, cyber-physical systems, and the Internet of Things (IoT). According to Silveira [2017], the foundation of Industry 4.0 is that interconnected machines, systems, and assets enable the creation of intelligent networks capable of operating autonomously.

In this context, quality inspection stands out as an essential process to ensure that final products meet required standards. The objective of this proposal is to implement IoT in the quality inspection sector, representing an advance in

the optimization of production lines with early fault detection, minimization of downtime, and process adaptation according to the type of error identified.

II. BACKGROUND AND APPLICATIONS

A. Computer Vision

According to Ballard and Brown [1982], computer vision can be defined as a science that studies and develops technologies enabling machines to “see” and extract features from the environment through images captured by different types of sensors and devices. From this information, it is possible to recognize, manipulate, and process data about the objects that compose the captured image.

Barelli [2018] states that computer vision studies and implements systems capable of “seeing” through artificial processes, carried out with the aid of hardware and software. He also highlights that artificial intelligence is fundamental in this context, as it contributes to the improvement of image processing techniques and pattern recognition. These steps are essential for the system to identify and classify objects present in the analyzed images.

Comparing the two definitions, Ballard and Brown [1982] adopts a more conceptual view, focused on the machine’s ability to capture and extract information, whereas Barelli [2018] focuses on technology and the role of AI in “artificial vision”. Both authors agree that the central objective is for machines to understand and interpret the visual environment in a manner similar to humans.

According to Barelli [2018], computer vision systems typically follow a common workflow (Figure 1):

- 1) **Image acquisition:** sensors capture and digitize the image to be analyzed.
- 2) **Pre-processing:** improves image quality and facilitates interpretation.
- 3) **Segmentation:** isolates objects of interest from the rest of the image.
- 4) **High-level processing:** recognizes and classifies objects into predefined categories.

Fig. 1. Workflow of a Computer Vision-based system.
Source: Barelli [2018].

B. Machine Learning

The Python programming language provides numerous functions that act as building blocks for executing tasks, aiming to simplify development and make code more efficient. In addition, libraries such as PyTorch, focused on machine learning, can be utilized.

Pointer [2019] states that PyTorch is an open-source offering that facilitates writing deep learning code in Python. It has two lineages: the first derives many concepts and features from Torch, a Lua-based neural network library whose origins date back to 2002; the second is Chainer, created in Japan in 2015, which was one of the first neural network libraries to offer an agile approach to differentiation instead of defining static graphs, allowing greater flexibility in how networks are created, trained, and operated.

According to Bergmann and Stryker [2025], any machine learning algorithm, even those applied to non-numerical information such as sounds or images, requires data to be represented in numerical form through tensors.

PyTorch modules function as building blocks that facilitate the creation of neural networks, avoiding extensive manual coding. They also provide support for working with text, images, audio, and popular architectures such as ResNet.

III. METHODOLOGY

Scientific methodology is essential to ensure the reliability and reproducibility of results [Marconi and Lakatos, 2017]. This project aims to contribute to the development and validation of a product quality analysis system based on Artificial Intelligence (AI) techniques; results are evaluated by numerical performance metrics. The following procedure was defined:

A. Scope Definition

As argued by Souza et al. [2020], prior scope definition is fundamental to ensure the effectiveness of training computer vision models. In this stage, the types of defects to be identified were established: stains, tears, finishing failures, and discoloration. Additionally, the cut-resistant glove was defined as the object of study.

B. Data Collection

This stage is fundamental for carrying out the analyses. Images used in this project were obtained by the authors

themselves, captured in a controlled environment (Figure 2), with the objective of simulating the real industrial inspection process and ensuring classification quality. The dataset used for training the neural network consisted of 50 images of gloves, divided into two distinct classes: `no_defect` and `defect`.

Fig. 2. Controlled environment for image capture.
Source: Authors, 2025.

C. Data Pre-processing

This stage contributes to improving the generalization capacity of the neural network, reducing overfitting problems [Goodfellow et al., 2016]. Collected images undergo standardization steps: resizing, color correction, brightness adjustment, and duplicate removal. Data augmentation is also applied, consisting of rotations, flips, brightness variations, and noise, broadening training diversity and reducing the risk of the model memorizing patterns specific to the original images.

Images were resized to 256 pixels and center-cropped to 224×224 pixels, the standard used by ResNet. They were then converted to tensors and normalized using the mean and standard deviation of the ImageNet dataset, ensuring standardized pixel distribution.

D. AI Model Development

The Artificial Intelligence model was developed in Visual Studio Code using Python. The technique of Transfer Learning

was adopted, applied to the ResNet-18 architecture implemented via the PyTorch library. ResNet-18 is a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) known for its 18 layers (including 17 main hidden layers) and residual blocks, which facilitate training by allowing gradient flow through alternative paths, thereby reducing vanishing gradient problems.

The original output layer of ResNet-18 was modified to suit the binary classification problem. In the convolutional blocks, the activation function used is ReLU (Rectified Linear Unit), while the final classification step uses Softmax implicitly through the loss function employed during training. The resulting model has approximately 11.7 million trainable parameters, reflecting its capacity to capture complex patterns.

E. Model Training

Following the recommendations of Goodfellow et al. [2016], the code is divided into three categories: 70% training, 15% validation, and 15% testing. Throughout training, hyperparameters such as number of layers, activation function, learning rate, and number of epochs were adjusted. Regularization techniques such as dropout and batch normalization may also be applied to increase robustness.

The model was trained on the development machine's CPU. The dataset used 25 images for training and 25 for validation, over 30 epochs (`NUM_EPOCHS = 30`). The optimizer used was SGD (Stochastic Gradient Descent) with a learning rate of 0.001 (`LEARNING_RATE = 0.001`). Total training time from the first to the last epoch was 34 seconds. The best model checkpoint was saved at epoch 8, when the validation accuracy reached 1.00 for the first time.

F. Performance Evaluation

Performance evaluation is fundamental for monitoring progress and identifying successes and failures. Sammut and Webb [2017] recommends verifying results using classification metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and confusion matrix. Through the interpretation of these metrics, it is possible to distinguish false positives (improper approval of defective parts) and false negatives (improper rejection of correct parts).

G. Prototype Implementation

Prototyping is an essential step to verify the practical viability of the model in a productive environment [Zhang et al., 2021]. After validation, a functional prototype was developed capable of receiving images in real time and automatically issuing an “approved” or “rejected” decision.

The real-time inspection prototype was implemented on a notebook with the following specifications: 11th Gen Intel® Core™ i5-1135G7 @ 2.40 GHz (2.42 GHz), 8.00 GB RAM (usable: 7.78 GB), 64-bit OS with x64 architecture, Intel® Iris® Xe Graphics 3.9 GB. Execution was performed using the script `real_time_inspection.py`, responsible for integrating video capture, loading the trained model, and issuing decisions based on neural network predictions.

IV. SYSTEM MODELING AND STRUCTURE

System modeling and structure consist of an organized representation of its components, functions, and interactions. This process uses diagrams and technical descriptions to illustrate the information flow, system behavior, and relationships between its parts. The goal is to facilitate understanding, planning, and implementation of the solution, ensuring all elements work in an integrated and coherent manner.

A. Pipeline

The pipeline visually demonstrates the organization and procedure employed in this project: research into the best quality analysis approach; code assembly and its functionality; AI training; processing of data to be analyzed; identification and detection by the camera; data presentation; testing phase; and, finally, decision-making.

B. Activity Diagram

The activity diagram represents the flow of actions or steps of a process within a system, showing the sequence of operations and decision points. It is useful for describing the use-case diagram.

For this work, the activity diagram presents the quality inspection process flow, which begins with image acquisition via the camera. The subsequent step allows the system to analyze data and verify the existence of defects in the part. If the system identifies a defect, the IoT-connected platform presents the count and the “Rejected” status, and the product is directed to the reject area; otherwise, the platform presents the count and the “Approved” status, and the process continues normally. This cycle is continuously repeated, forming an operational loop.

C. Use Case Diagram

The use case diagram, elaborated in VisualParadigm software, allows a simplified visualization of the main actors' requirements. The operator has the requirement of inserting the part and only receiving the result. The inspection system, on the other hand, executes the central functions: feature extraction, part classification, and decision issuance to the operator. Subsequently, it triggers a set of crucial actions for real-time communication: status signaling (LED) via serial communication with Arduino (indicating Approved/Rejected); result communication via speech synthesis (providing conditional auditory feedback); and transmission of operational data to the IoT platform (Thingier.io), enabling remote monitoring. In the backend, the database is responsible for training the model, evaluating performance, and collecting process data as instructed by the technician.

D. Class Diagram

The class diagram aids in visualizing the structure of a system, displaying classes, their attributes, methods, and relationships between them.

The training diagram shows that the structure initiates its flow through the `PipelineTreinamento` class

controller, which manages the learning dependencies such as the optimizer and criterion. The key classes control the central ResNet18 component and highlight the CustomGloveDataset class, which inherits and customizes data loading by applying specific transformations such as image cropping, to ensure the quality of the inputs used in training.

The real-time inspection operation diagram reflects the modular architecture of the application, simulating the production inspection environment. The RealTimeController class initiates and orchestrates the operation. The CameraCapturer is responsible for data acquisition via OpenCV. The ModelPredictor encapsulates the model (ResNet-18) and applies classification to each frame. The RealTimeController then uses this data to apply the decision rule and trigger communication functionalities. The SerialCommunicator (for Arduino and LEDs) and FeedbackHandler (for speech synthesis via Pyttsx3) manage physical and auditory feedback to the operator. Finally, the IoTManager is responsible for periodically sending count data and status to the Thingier.io platform, ensuring the entire process is recorded and monitored in real time.

E. Sequence Diagram

The sequence diagram details the dynamic and continuous flow of the inspection, with the RealTimeController acting as the central orchestrator of the system. The process runs in a continuous data acquisition loop, in which the CameraCapturer obtains a frame that is sent to the ModelPredictor for real-time inference using the ResNet-18 model. After classification and application of the decision rule, the RealTimeController triggers, in parallel, the feedback and communication mechanisms: the SerialCommunicator is contacted to send the visual signaling command to the Arduino (LEDs); the FeedbackHandler is activated to trigger speech synthesis (conditional on status change); and the IoTManager is triggered for periodic data and counter transmission to the Thingier.io platform. This cycle ensures that the result and operational status are communicated to the operator visually, auditorily, and remotely at each processed frame, ceasing only upon user intervention.

F. Programming Code

The code is composed of two main modules: the Training and Evaluation Module and the Real-Time Inspection Module, both developed in Python. The diagrams presented previously help to understand the functioning of the modular, Deep Learning-based quality inspection solution, using the PyTorch framework and the OpenCV library.

1) *Training and Evaluation Module*: The Training and Evaluation Module (`train_classifier.py`) is responsible for building the classifier using the Transfer Learning technique based on the pre-trained ResNet-18 architecture. The development and execution of this module were supported

by the PyTorch (`torch.nn`, `torch.optim`) and torchvision libraries (for image manipulation and Data Augmentation), NumPy (for numerical operations), and Scikit-learn (`sklearn.metrics`) for metric calculation. The model was adapted for binary classification, separating defective from non-defective products by replacing the final layer with a linear layer of two outputs, while keeping the initial convolutional layers frozen. The training pipeline includes Data Augmentation strategies and rigorous validation, ensuring greater robustness and generalization. Performance is evaluated through F1-Score and Confusion Matrix metrics, and the final result is the storage of model weights in the file `best_luva_classifier.pth`.

2) *Real-Time Inspection Module*: The Real-Time Inspection Module (`real_time_inspection.py`) simulates the production environment, integrating the trained model with video capture. The script uses PyTorch and torchvision to load and run the Transfer Learning model (ResNet-18), and the OpenCV (`cv2`) library for camera capture, processing, and video display (Computer Vision). The system performs continuous inference, processing and classifying each video frame in real time. Decision-making occurs in an automated manner, based on a rule (e.g., predictions above 80% for the `no_defect` class). The system provides visual and auditory feedback in the camera feed and also on the Thingier.io platform, via the `requests` library for HTTP communication, indicating whether the part has been “Approved” or “Rejected”.

G. IoT

To ensure real-time system monitoring and promote clear, remote interpretation, the IoT platform Thingier.io was used. A dashboard was developed on this platform, allowing operators to track the status of gloves in real time, identifying whether they are approved or rejected in the quality test. The system also enables control of the count of approved and rejected gloves in the analyses performed.

For this integration to be possible, it was necessary to prepare both the data-sending and the data-receiving environments. Communication between them was established via the HTTP protocol, which allows information to be sent to the platform simply and directly, following the client-server model in which the client device sends data to the server using commands such as GET and POST.

The system was configured to send data every 60 seconds due to a limitation of the platform’s free plan. Initially, these data are sent to a device that collects the information and transfers it to a data bucket responsible for intermediate storage. Subsequently, the information is sent to the dashboard, which presents results intuitively to operators.

H. Arduino

The Arduino implementation aims to indicate the glove status to the operator via LEDs. If the system identifies a defective glove, the red LED is activated, indicating that the quality was rejected. Conversely, if the system identifies a

Fig. 3. Confusion Matrix.
Source: Authors, 2025.

glove without defects, the green LED is turned on, informing that the product quality was approved. Two main steps are required: first, assembling the circuit with the LEDs and uploading the program to the Arduino via the Arduino IDE software; second, programming in Python using the PySerial library, which allows Visual Studio Code to establish serial communication with the Arduino and send control commands (e.g., ‘A’ for Approved and ‘R’ for Rejected).

I. Speech Synthesis

In addition to visual indication, auditory indication was implemented through the integration of speech synthesis into the code. The system provides the operator with audio feedback indicating whether the glove was approved or rejected in the inspection process. This speech synthesis is triggered only on status changes; that is, if the system repeatedly and sequentially identifies a glove as approved, the audio will be reproduced only once, and a new synthesis will occur only when the status changes (e.g., from “approved” to “rejected”).

This functionality is made possible by the Pyttsx3 library, which allows offline voice message generation. Additionally, the use of the `threading` library ensures that voice reproduction does not block the main OpenCV video capture loop, ensuring fluidity in inspection and clarity in communication during the process.

V. RESULTS

The final model evaluation, performed on an independent test set, showed satisfactory performance: accuracy of 0.90, precision of 1.00, recall of 0.80, F1-Score of 1.00, and Loss of 0.4689. The Confusion Matrix (Table 3) recorded zero false positives and zero false negatives, confirming the robustness of the system in differentiating gloves with and without defects.

In a practical validation composed of 100 samples (50 defective and 50 non-defective), simulating an industrial environment, the system achieved an accuracy of 89%. This value was affected by the occurrence of 11 cases classified

as Undefined, which limited overall performance. Among the samples that received a model decision, results were robust: all 50 non-defective gloves were correctly classified (100%), while 39 of the 50 defective gloves were correctly identified (78%).

In terms of operational performance, gloves classified as Rejected showed an average confidence of 0.68 compared to 0.66 for Approved gloves. The inference time was higher for Rejected gloves (43.57 ms) than for Approved ones (42.46 ms), indicating greater visual complexity during the processing of defective images.

The figures, diagrams, and code developed in this work are available in a public repository on GitHub at: https://github.com/IMangiaB/Sistema_de_analise_de_qualidade_de_produto_s.

VI. CONCLUSION

The development of this project allowed validation of the application of Computer Vision and Machine Learning techniques for the automatic inspection of industrial products. The use of the ResNet-18 architecture with Transfer Learning proved efficient in distinguishing defective from non-defective gloves, presenting high performance metrics during the testing phase.

The integration of the model with real-time video capture, IoT platform, light signals via Arduino, and speech synthesis enhanced the robustness and usability of the system, making the inspection environment more agile, safer, and less dependent on human intervention. Results indicate that intelligent solutions can strengthen quality control, especially in environments that require speed and precision.

Despite satisfactory performance, it is recommended to expand the dataset, include new types of defects, and conduct tests in a real industrial environment to increase the model’s generalization capacity. As a future improvement, the use of algorithms such as YOLO and tools such as makesense.ai is

indicated to increase reliability and precision in neural network training and real-time camera reading.

Thus, this work demonstrates that the integration of Artificial Intelligence, Computer Vision, and IoT represents a solid path toward the modernization of industrial processes, contributing to Industry 4.0 and evidencing the role of intelligent automation as a continuous improvement tool.

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